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Significance of Extreme Reflection Angles in RIS-assisted Wireless Networks

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Abstract—This study examines the importance of the extreme reflection angles in terms of the spectral efficiency in a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) - assisted wireless communication system. The investigation considers practical RIS unit cells with a non-ideal reflection response, which is typical, especially when the extreme angles of incidence, as well as reflection, are considered. A significant disparity was found in spectral efficiency when RIS is employed to reflect signals at extreme angles, with a notable 150% – 200% increase in the required number of unit cells to maintain the same spectral efficiency compared to scenarios with normal reflection angles. This observation underscores the importance of considering reflection angles in the design and optimization of RIS hardware. The results contribute valuable insights to the understanding of RIS behaviour in practical scenarios, paving the way for enhanced spectral efficiency and improved network performance.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, Spectral Efficiency, Extreme Reflection Angles

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) is transforming wireless communication by dynamically manipulating radio signal propagation to optimize network performance at the physical layer [1]. RIS utilizes passive reflecting elements to control amplitude and phase changes in incoming signals, addressing challenges related to signal fading and interference. This approach not only improves spectral and energy efficiency but also promotes sustainable growth in wireless networks [2]. However, integrating RIS seamlessly into wireless networks presents challenges, such as optimizing reflection response in a wide angular range, developing precise channel models, ensuring energy efficiency of RIS hardware, and formulating practical deployment strategies [3]. An underexplored dimension of RIS is the influence of extreme reflection angles on end-to-end spectral efficiency, requiring thorough investigation. Understanding RIS behavior across varying incident angles is crucial for overcoming challenges and optimizing deployment for superior network performance [4], [5], [6]. In addition to reflection angles, another important factor to consider is the impact of varying environmental conditions, such as mobility, obstacles, and interference, on

RIS performance [7]. While RIS has shown significant potential in controlled environments [8], real-world demands a deeper understanding of how these external factors [9] lead to multi-path components arriving at RIS from diverse angular directions that affect the system's overall spectral efficiency. Moreover, exploring the optimization of RIS hardware which is appropriate for such dynamic scenarios where users and devices are constantly moving, is essential for proper resource allocation, leading to maximizing its benefits. This work contributes towards this transformative potential of RIS and informs the hardware development cycle, leading to a pivotal shift in the future of network performance and efficiency.

II. SYSTEM MODEL WITH PRACTICAL RIS HARDWARE

In RIS-assisted communications, the interaction typically involves a Base Station (BS) and User Equipment (UE). This configuration leverages the inherent capabilities of RIS, which comprises an array of $M \times N$ row and column unit cells (or elements), enabling a reconfigurable reflection aperture, and allowing for dynamic adjustments of the reflected wave's angles. Conventionally, researchers consider ideal elements with uniform reflection coefficients, under the assumption that incident angles equate to *adjustable* reflection angles. However, this study deviates from this idealized model by incorporating practical elements, thereby delving into the real-world consequences of reflection angles. This investigation recognizes reflection angle variation from 0° to 90° .

In (1), H_{RIS} denotes the controllable channel between the receiver and transmitter via RIS, enabling the use of a parametric spatial model to express the channel via RIS as [10]

$$H_{RIS} = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_l q_l a_R(\theta_{R,l}, \phi_{R,l}) a_T^*(\theta_{T,l}, \phi_{T,l}) \quad (1)$$

Here, α_l denotes a complex scalar representing the path gain for the l -th path, excluding the influence of the RIS element. Similarly, q_l is a complex scalar signifying the controllable impact of the l -th RIS element. Additionally, a_R and a_T stand for the array steering vectors at the receiver and

Fig. 1. Illustration of RIS-assisted wireless communication system.

transmitter, respectively. Here, θ denotes the azimuth angle, and ϕ represents the elevation angle. For a complete system model description used in this paper, please refer to [11], [12].

To initiate the investigation, a general element was selected from existing literature to serve as the unit cell for building RIS [13] and then assessing path loss [14]. The focus is on reflection angles when the UE is positioned at various angles in relation to the RIS, described as θ_r in Fig. 1. For simplicity, we are using a single antenna transmitter and receiver. The initial configuration involved the RIS dominating reflection at a fixed angle, and subsequent movements of the UE were monitored. Here, $M = N = 20$, $d_t = d_r = 30$ meters, and operational frequency 28 GHz. For investigation purposes, we assume a widely used ideal condition where the reflection phase quantization is 1° , such that the RIS can be configured to provide maximum reflection directivity towards any given direction. Contrary to theoretical expectations of consistent reflection power, practical unit cells showed increased path loss and power dissipation, especially with UE movement from the initial position. On extreme angles, notably higher path loss was observed, highlighting challenges with practical unit cells in optimizing reflection response.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the integration of RIS, the adaptability of the system allows reconfiguration of the RIS to optimize directivity toward the UE's newly assumed position. However, our findings, as illustrated in Fig. 2, highlight a limitation when practical elements are employed. Here, the received signal power experienced by the UE varies as it moves. As such, the path loss at 30° is measured at -120 dB, but decays to -128 dB at 75° . It can be observed that sometimes the UE is bound to enter in particularly disadvantaged positions. Moreover, even if when UE is within the advantageous angular region, a diverse set of multi-path components is bound to arrive at RIS from these extreme directions when uplink is considered.

Fig. 3 further underscores the impact of these findings where the transmit power is 17 dBm, receiver and transmitter antenna

Fig. 2. Comparison between Path loss contours when the UE is sequentially moved from $\theta_r = 15^\circ$ to 75° , while $M = N = 20$ element RIS is reconfigured to serve it.

Fig. 3. Achievable spectral efficiency at UEs positioned at multiple θ_r , versus number of RIS elements. Insert: co-polarized reflection magnitude in V/m of the unit cell when periodicity is considered (normalized scale).

gain is considered to be 0 dBi, while the receiver noise floor is assumed to be at -90 dBm. With an RIS comprising of around 250 unit cells, the UE's spectral efficiency at 30° is calculated to be 7 bps/Hz, whereas it diminishes to 5.2 bps/Hz when the UE is positioned at 75° . This disparity emphasizes the practical implications of RIS deployment, particularly when considering the spectral efficiency variations experienced by UEs. Now let's see if we want to maintain the spectral efficiency, the cost to pay is the increase in the number of unit cells from 250 to around 380 at 60° , and as high as 500 at 75° . Thus, the effective distribution of resources such as power and frequency is crucial for serving UEs positioned at extreme angles relative to the BSs. While increasing the number of unit cells can help accommodate more UEs, it does not fully resolve the disparity in service quality between extreme-angle and low-angle UEs. UEs located at extreme

Fig. 4. Spectral efficiency at varying d_{RIS} versus number of RIS elements.

angles, particularly at the perimeter of the coverage area, often continue to experience suboptimal performance even with a higher number of unit cells. Therefore, optimizing resource allocation specifically for these extreme-angle UEs is also essential to ensure a more balanced and efficient service for all UEs, regardless of their angular position within the network.

These findings prompt a re-evaluation of conventional assumptions and emphasize the need to incorporate practical elements in RIS research for an accurate representation of real-world scenarios. The observed spectral efficiency variations call for a refined approach to RIS deployment, considering the dynamic nature of UE mobility within the RIS range.

In an additional scenario, both UE and BS are positioned at the same level, while the contribution of RIS is varied by increasing its distance from both, BS and the UE. To understand operational dynamics in this context, the variable d_{RIS} , representing the distance between the RIS and the BS/UE, was systematically varied while configuring RIS to serve the UE. In the trend, shown in Fig. 4, we observe a decrease in spectral efficiency with increasing values of d_{RIS} due to an increase in path-loss (see Fig. 1). Now, when the obstruction between the BS and UE is removed, introducing a dual-signal scenario—comprising the Line-of-Sight (LoS) signal from the BS and the RIS-aided signal, the impact of increasing the number of RIS elements is further cleared.

The results also suggest that in the presence of a LoS component, the additional signal provided by the RIS does not significantly enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which leads to minimal improvement in spectral efficiency. This observation highlights an important resource allocation principle, especially for UEs present in disadvantageous locations: RIS resources should be prioritized for users without LoS conditions. In such cases, the RIS can assist in improving spectral efficiency, as users without a strong direct signal path benefit more from the additional signal reflections. Conversely, allocating RIS resources to users with LoS conditions yields diminishing returns due to the already strong signal path present, thus offering limited performance gains. A decrease in spectral efficiency is also observed as d_{RIS} increases, which can be attributed to the corresponding rise in path loss with

distance. This outcome is expected, as greater distances generally result in higher path loss, leading to a decline in spectral efficiency, however, the trend it follows is interesting. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first time multi-facet considerations in RIS operation are reported when hardware development and resource allocation are considered side-by-side.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This investigation reveals a distinctive pattern in RIS-aided networks: extreme reflection angles require a significant 150% – 200% increase in the number of elements for equivalent spectral efficiency compared to normal incident angles. Contrary to expectations, the results reveal a non-linear relationship between spectral efficiency and the number of elements. This emphasizes the need for dedicated investigations focused on spectral efficiency-centric RIS design considerations and operational resource allocation for future smart radio environments.

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